

Andrej Poleev • Postfach 301812 • 10746 Berlin

Queen Elizabeth II and members of the Royal family
Buckingham Palace
London SW1A 1AA
United Kindgom

21.02.2019

Dethronement of Elizabeth II and termination of British monarchy.

Due to disregard of my requests of 28.09.2018, 15.12.2018, 18.12.2018 and 11.02.2019 caused by irresponsibility, legal incompetence and mental incapacity of inquired persons, I dethrone Elizabeth II, as from now the former Queen of the Great Britain and the United Kingdom, and declare her authority or directives lapse with immediate effect. Consequentially, the British monarchy is ceased and I seize its property; these seizure and cessation of royalty are valid immediately and irrevocable.

Dr. Andrej Poleev

References.

Letters of 28.09.2018 addressed to Director of the National Crime Agency, to Secretary of Home Office and to Royal Courts of Justice, United Kingdom.

<http://constitution.fund/letters/UK.pdf>

Letters of 15.12.2018 addressed to Mayor of London, to Mayor's Office for Policing and Crime, to Head of Police & Crime Committee of the London Assembly, and to Metropolitan Police.

<http://constitution.fund/letters/London.pdf>

Request for Mutual Legal Assistance in Criminal Matters of 18.12.2018 addressed to Office of Financial Sanction Implementation, to Central Authority, to Serious Fraud Office, United Kingdom.

<http://constitution.fund/letters/MLA.pdf>

Request for payment of 11.02.2019 addressed to Bank of England.

<http://constitution.fund/letters/bill.pdf>

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To Elisabeth and other members of the Windsor family
Buckingham Palace
London SW1A 1AA
Great Britain

9.04.2019

The house ban.

Referring to my declaration of 21.02.2019, I prohibit everybody any entrance or usage of my property without my permission. Therefore, all members of the Windsor Family and attendants are requested to leave immediately the Buckingham Palace, Windsor Castle, Palace of Holyroodhouse, Hillsborough Castle, Sandringham House and others, for which I am legal possessor since 21.02.2019, and hand me over the keys. In case of violation of my rights, I will issue International Arrest Warrants against lawbreakers.

Dr. Andrej Poleev

Reference.

Declaration of 21.02.2019.

<http://constitution.fund/letters/dethronement.pdf>